

Big Tech Disruption: The changing role of the traditional bank

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ABSTRACT

Big Tech companies have been disrupting several markets by their disruptive technologies. One of the next sectors that will face disruption by Big Tech is the banking sector. The mix of different technologies Big Tech companies offer makes it a potential competitor for traditional banks. A company like Apple has its own phones, operating system (iOS), messenger app and payment function. This gives Big Tech companies an advantage to integrate financial technologies (FinTech). Disruptive events are a factor in the adoption rate of new financial technologies. They create an unexpected change in people's everyday lives. This research looks into how the entry of Big Tech companies and disruptive events affect the adoption rate of new financial technologies and the role of the traditional bank. The insights created by this research shows that the role of the traditional bank will change and that disruptive events accelerate the adoption rate of FinTech.

Keywords

Big Tech, FinTech, FinTech adoption, Disruptive events, Traditional bank

INTRODUCTION

In recent years in nearly all sectors companies have adopted new technologies. The digital transformation trend is ongoing and Big Tech companies are a driving force behind the movement (Kretschmer, T., & Khashabi, P., 2020). Besides Big Tech companies, disruptive events affect the pace at which new technologies are adopted by end-users and companies. According to Saliola & Islam (2020): "The pandemic has pushed societies to an inflection point where embracing technology is no longer an option but a necessity." Big Tech companies are growing and so is their impact.

The banking sector has seen a rise of new technologies under the name FinTech (Financial technology). Big Tech companies have a particularly strong proposition when it comes to FinTech. By using a mix of their technologies and reach, Big Tech companies are able to distribute FinTech at a rapid rate (Padilla & de la Mano, 2018).

In China the use of FinTech has already been widely accepted in the form of the messenger app WeChat and mobile payments. In 2018 mobile payments counted for 16% of the GDP in China. Besides mobile payments, Big Tech companies also give out personal loans in China (Agustín Carstens.,2018).

Financial Technologies

According to Folwarski (2020) the FinTech sector is composed of entities dealing with: Credit, payments, investments management services and market support financial services. FinTech companies use innovative technologies to differ themselves from traditional banks who do not always keep up with the latest technology developments (Folwarski, 2020). Big Tech companies are a bigger threat to traditional banks than most FinTech companies because of their already existing reputation, brands, customer base and technologies. Big Tech companies have an advantage when it comes to technology in banking (Padilla & de la Mano, 2018).

This study will look into the entry of Big Tech companies in the banking sector and how their entry affects the adoption rate of new financial technologies. Because of Big Tech's customer base, brands and technologies the adoption rate of FinTech will potentially increase. Besides the entry of Big Tech companies this research will also look into the adoption rate of FinTech after and during disruptive events. Finally, this research looks into the role of the traditional bank and how this might change after the wide adoption of FinTech.

Managerial Relevance

Financial services are one of the most important aspects in every person's life. With the entrance of Big Tech in the financial market and the new FinTech which are adopted, new opportunities will originate for all sectors and companies.

Academic Relevance

This research investigates the impact of disruptive events and the entry of Big Tech companies in the banking sector on the accelerated adoption of new financial technologies and the role of traditional banks. Research on this topic has not taken place before and this research can be a valuable contribution to the academic world.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research will focus on what impact the entry of Big Tech companies in the banking sector have on the accelerated adoption of new financial technologies and the changing role of traditional banks. Literature showed that the banking sector is influenced by the entry of Big Tech companies and that the role of the traditional banks is changing. The entry of Big Tech companies within a certain industry brings changes due to the access of multiple platforms of these companies. As existing literature falls short in telling if the adoption rate of new financial technologies is affected by the entry of Big Tech companies, there is a clear knowledge gap between these subjects. To further investigate this knowledge gap, the problem statement will be formulated on the basis of a few different topics.

New Technologies

The banking industry is known as a relatively conservative industry (Leventis et al., 2013) where the adoption of new technologies can be problematic due to the technological infrastructure and deep organizational changes within this industry. (Cuesta et al., 2015). This research will not focus on the adoption of these new technologies in the conservative banking industry specifically, only on the aspects of the accelerated adoption of these new technologies due to the entry of Big Tech companies. The technologies that are included in the research are FinTech (Financial Technology) developments. (Leong, K. and Sung, A., 2018)

Issues

The accelerated adoption of new technologies and the changing role of traditional banks is influenced by issues that are present with the adoption of new technologies. A sensitive topic within the banking industry as well as Big Tech

companies is privacy. The entry of Big Tech companies in the banking industry has already caused questions about topics concerning privacy, including data sharing, antitrust intervention and enforcing privacy protection (Padilla & de la Mano., 2018). The second issue which is included in the perception of the usefulness of Financial Technology. The perceived usefulness can be interpreted as the prediction of acceptance and use of new information technology (software and information systems) within organizations. (Wu, Hsueh-Ying et al., 2010)

The third issue which is included in this research is the Law and Regulation of Financial Technologies. Due to different regulations across the world and the different criteria which the Financial Technologies must comply with (Madir, n.d.), the issue is stated that Financial Technology must comply with it. The last issue which can influence the accelerated adoption of Financial Technologies is the monopoly position within the industry. Big Tech companies operate on multiple platforms, due to these cross-business activities they can cross-subsidize business in one of their own platforms and increase other platforms, which can lead to platform envelopment. (Padilla & de la Mano., 2018)

Disruptive Events and the entrance of Big Tech companies

The third topic is included in the occurrence of disruptive events and their influence on the accelerated adoption of Financial Technologies. A Disruptive event is organizational-wide emergencies and disasters which are not covered by routine measures (BCM Institute, 2020). The occurrence can either positively or negatively influence the adoption rate of these Financial Technologies. This research will include practical examples from the last 20 years and how these events did influence the adoption rate of technology. The final aspect which will be addressed in this research is the entrance of Big Tech Companies in the financial industry. The entry of these companies changes the role of traditional banking.

Knowledge gap

After integrating literary theory into the problem statement, a lack of understanding emerged on how disruptive events, FinTech and the entry of Big Tech companies affect the role of traditional banks, which will be further explored in the following sections.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Given the established knowledge gap, the following problem statement is formulated:

“What impact do disruptive events and the entry of Big Tech Companies in the banking sector have on the accelerated adoption of new financial technologies and the role of traditional banks?”

In order to answer this problem statement, more investigation is needed about the entrance of Big Tech companies, disruptive events and the impact of accelerated adoption of FinTech on the role of traditional banks.

The first theoretical question is formulated to form a definition of FinTech. The second question is to provide the required elaboration about the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market. In addition, two theoretical questions are formulated to demonstrate the relation between the disruptive events, FinTech and the role of traditional banks.

- What is FinTech?
- What are the consequences of the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market?
- How do disruptive events affect the accelerated adoption of FinTech?
- To what extent does FinTech affect the current role of the bank?

Subsequently, two practical questions are composed to research the relationship between the FinTech, the accelerated adoption and the changing role of traditional banks. Moreover, the moderating effect of disruptive events and the entrance of Big Tech companies are measured.

- To what extent does the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market affect the adoption of FinTech and change the traditional banks?
- To what extent does the accelerated adoption of FinTech due to disruptive events, affect the role of traditional banks?

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

In this research ‘FinTech’ is the independent variable. The term ‘FinTech’ means in the literal sense financial and technologies. This means using state-of-the-art telecommunications and IT technology solutions to improve the process of providing financial services (Storey & Christopher, 1999). Fintech also means combining financial and digital services in increasingly individualized technologies using databases (big data) (Hannan, H, & J. Nellie, 1993). In our research we combined the two definitions and define FinTech activities as making online payments, mobile payments, advanced transactional banking, virtual currencies and innovative solutions in the field of investment funds as well as database management.

The changing role of traditional banks is the dependent variable. The relationship between the independent and dependent variable is partially explained by the mediator ‘accelerated adoption of FinTech’. The rate of adoption is the place at which a new technology is acquired and used by the public. The rate is represented by the number of members of a society who start using a new technology or innovation during a specific period of time (Kenton, 2020).

The moderating variables ‘disruptive events’ and the ‘entrance of Big Tech companies’ influence the adoption of FinTech by the users. A disruptive event is already described in the problem statement section. This results in the following hypotheses:

H1: Disruptive events positively affect the adoption of FinTech.

The entrance of Big Tech companies is believed to be a quasi-moderator as it has a direct influence on the accelerated adoption and on the changing role of traditional banks, Miguel & Jorge (2019) state that the entry of Big Tech companies into the financial market has a significant impact on competition, as they have large installed customer bases, established reputations, powerful brands, considerable earnings, and unfettered access to capital markets. In addition, they can leverage superior information about consumer preferences and habits. The hypotheses below are based on this section:

H2: The entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market will have a negative effect on the role of traditional banks.

The accelerated adoption of the new FinTech, in combination with the entrance of Big Tech companies, will lead to a changing role of traditional banks. Currently, a traditional bank is described as an institution whose current operations

consist in granting loans and receiving deposits from the public (Freixas & Rochet, 2008). FinTech and Big Tech companies are increasing competition in the financial markets and providing services that traditional banks do less efficiently or not at all (Giorgio, Giacomo, & Alberto, 2017). Therefore, banks have to change their role and adopt new technological innovations themselves. This section results into the last hypotheses:

H3: As the adoption of FinTech is accelerated by new FinTech, disruptive events or the arrival of Big Tech companies, traditional banks have to change their role to remain competitive in the market.

METHODOLOGY

Literature Research

For the theoretical research questions existing literature has been reviewed to form a conclusive answer. The literature which is used for the results section is purely academic literature which is peer-reviewed and relevant for this research. The results of the literature research can be found in the results chapter.

Survey Research

The second part of the methodology is the survey research. The survey is conducted to answer the practical research questions. The survey was distributed on Tuesday 10/11/20. To determine the final sample for the survey, the four steps to determine the final sample are stated. The four steps are: defining the population, defining the sampling frame, determining the sampling design and determining the sample size of the sampling process.

The first step is to define the population for this survey. The population of this research is Dutch people that recently used Financial Technology. Because this population was too wide-ranging for the final sample the convenience sampling technique was used. The sample consisted of 35 (N=35) people who are between the ages of 18 en 35. With this sample there was a homogeneous sample wherein the respondents had the same age range and the same level of education. Due to the aging range there was a higher probability an user had experience with a Financial Technology (Liébana-Cabanillas & et al, 2015). All participants in this research received the same way of intervention, in this research only one group was used. After the survey was constructed it was tested by three individuals to confirm if the survey had the desired effect and the corresponding questions were valid.

Measurements

To measure the dependent variable (Changing Role of traditional banks) questions were asked in the survey that are related to this topic. The questions are related to the attitude of the participants towards FinTech and traditional banks and how the recent disruptive events changed this attitude. The measurements that are used are multi-item measurements. The questions are customized and not off-the-shelf, this choice was made because there was no good framework available for this survey purpose. To measure the independent variable (FinTech) two to three questions were asked in the survey. These questions also used a multi-item measurement scale. The independent variable is measured as the use of FinTech, this to correlate with the other questions in the survey.

Validity

To increase the validity of this research a few steps were taken. All participants get the same treatment for the survey research, they got a textual instruction about the survey which was included in the survey. This instruction stated the general idea of the survey and explained the background of the research. Secondly all the questions are multi-item measurement scales, this to increase the validity due to higher construct validity and increased criterion validity (Sarstedt, Marko and Wilczynski, P., 2009).

Due to the choice of using convenience sampling the external validity of this research may be low. The choice for convenience sampling is made because of time limitations and the availability of a representative subsample. The results of the survey are only Dutch participants, these results could differ from results from other countries.

Measurement Reliability

To measure the correlation between the different variables the Cronbach's Alphas are calculated. Because there is only one independent variable an One Way ANOVA test is used to check the reliability. The results of the included items are considered acceptable when the values of the Cronbach's Alpha are above .7. The results of the survey are explained in the results of this research, an alpha of 0.05 is used to check this. In the table stated below the included items are stated, including the different values of Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's Alphas are calculated before (including all questions about the item) and after, the Cronbach's Alphas increased by removing two questions in each item.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha

Included Items	Cronbach's Alpha Before	Cronbach's Alpha After
FinTech Q1, Q2 & Q3	0.609	0.751
Changing Role TR Bank Q5, Q7 & Q9	0.643	0.718

RESULTS

In this section a literature analysis is conducted to discuss the theoretical research questions. Thereafter, a survey is designed to answer the last two practical questions. The first theoretical question about 'What is FinTech' is already answered in the explanation of the visual model.

The consequences of the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market

The entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market will transform the banking industry in radical ways. In the short term the entrance of the Big Tech companies may be seen as a good thing, as they increase competition to the benefit of the consumers. However, the lack of seeing the big picture in this case is hazardous, as Big Tech companies monopolize the distribution of loans to customers within a few years. This monopolization will have a huge impact on consumer welfare and financial instability (Miguel & Jorge, 2019). Moreover, there are three main issues of the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market. At first the privacy aspect. More and more data will be generated about customers and will persist under the control of Big Tech companies. Subjective data about customers and their habitats for the purposes of knowing, controlling, and modifying behavior. Many of the practices challenged social norms associated with privacy and laws (Zuboff, 2015). Although consumers do care about privacy (Jai & King, 2016); (Regner & Riener, 2017), they seem to be resigned about having to surrender their personal data to be able to make use of the Big Tech platforms and thereby accept that their data is no longer private (Turow, Hennessy, & Draper, 2015). Moreover, the control of the data is done by the Big Tech companies themselves, which hand them even more power over the customer (Stjernfelt & Lauritzen, 2020). With the additional financial data they get from the customers, there is a great risk for data security issues. The current hidden controls and privacy policies are being questioned with customers becoming increasingly nervous about the

level of control those Big Tech companies exert over their lives (Miguel & Jorge, 2019); (Stjernfelt & Lauritzen, 2020). This lack of transparency surrounding the Big Tech companies makes many customers feel uneasy (Emilio, 2007). With the current controls of Big Tech companies, they are still able to reject a loan based on their customers using proprietary data from their online platforms, social media and customers' digital footprint. Traditional banks cannot perform the same analyses due to regulations of the law (Carstens, 2019).

The effect of disruptive events on the accelerated adoption of FinTech

To analyse whether disruptive events affect an accelerated adoption of FinTech, academic literature is searched about two major disruptive events: the financial crisis in 2008 and the COVID-19 virus in 2019. At first the financial crisis in 2008, which stopped the flow of money through the banking system (Mellor, 2009). Consequences of the crisis where among others that it triggered new regulatory initiatives and accelerated existing ones (Philippon, 2016). These new financial conditions supported the emergence of FinTech (Arner, Barberis, & Buckley, 2009); (Kelly, 2014). Because of this, FinTech companies develop products and services that are outside the scope of financial regulators (Douglas & Armin, 2018). This resulted in a huge increase in the volume of worldwide investments in FinTech companies (Accenture, 2015). Bloomberg (2016) even states that without the financial crisis, there would be no FinTech. A decade after the financial crisis, the world experiences another disruptive event, the COVID-19 pandemic. This pandemic has impacted most of the world's economies, the financial sector, and the development of new financial technologies by FinTech companies. Despite FinTech is facing its first ever recession (Dariusz, 2020), their technology helped to keep the financial system working by facilitating financial flows in an online mode (Arner D. , et al., 2020). The trend of working with online financial flows continues as most governments will promote an accelerated transition to a cashless economy (Wójcik & Ioannou, 2020). In addition, the pandemic is likely to accelerate investment in digital infrastructure, which can be used by FinTech and boost its expansion (Arner D. , et al., 2020). Empirical proof is given by Fu & Mishra (2020), they documented mobile application data from 74 countries during COVID-19 to analyse the effects of the pandemic on the adoption of digital finance and FinTech. They estimated that the pandemic has led to between a 24 and 32 percent increase (5.2 to 6.3 million) in the relative rate of daily downloads of finance mobile applications in the sample countries.

The effect of FinTech on the changing role of traditional banks

The role of traditional banks consists of three sets of activities: transmuting the characteristics of financial assets and liabilities, providing payment services, and finally collecting and processing information (Giorgio, Giacomo, & Alberto, 2017). The effect of FinTech on each activity is analyzed with academic literature.

The first key activity of banks is to transmute the characteristics of financial assets and liabilities. Banks can set aside a limited buffer of liquid assets to grant longer-term loans, because it is very unlikely that every depositor withdraws all their funds the same time. This is the essence of banks' ability to provide liquidity services (Bryant, 1980); (Diamond & Dybvig, 1983). Currently, large FinTech companies can raise funds and put them in a pool, from which depositors can make withdrawals when needed. However, if they use these funds to grant longer-term loans, they would be acting by definition as banks and then they get more regulation. Second, is the ability to provide payment services. Currently, banks provide customers the opportunity to make payments directly from their deposit account or withdraw cash at ATMs. FinTech companies can provide the same services, but with less interest rates (Giorgio, Giacomo, & Alberto, 2017). Namely because FinTech has lighter regulatory requirements and better technologies (Fung, Lee, Yeh, & Yuen, 2020); (Klus, Lohwasser, Holotiuk, & Moormann, 2019). That's why Giorgio, Giacomo, & Alberto (2017) expect technological convergence between banks and FinTech. The final activity is about collecting and processing information. The type of information that banks have and the way they use it to take their decisions is a crucial element to determine the impact of FinTech on banks (Giorgio, Giacomo, & Alberto, 2017). Currently, traditional banks are using soft and relationship-based data. In contrast, FinTech is using big data and machine learning to predict preferences and behaviour (Thakor, July 2020); (Nicoletti, 2017). However, the problem for most FinTech companies is that customer information is private and only accessible for platforms with a large customer base. Banks do have such large customer bases, only they lack in processing data the right way due to ICT facilities (Klus, Lohwasser, Holotiuk, & Moormann, 2019).

The effect of the entrance of Big Tech companies in the financial market on the adoption of FinTech and changing role of traditional banks

Next, a survey study is designed. At first, it demonstrates that on average the trust in banks is higher than the trust in BigTech companies. This could be because 66% of the participants agree that a financial institution like a bank is the only

institution that should handle financial information. In contrast, the results show that more than half of the participants prefer convenience over privacy when using technologies. In addition, they also indicate that they will choose FinTech from Big Tech companies over FinTech from banks when technologies of Big Tech companies are easier to use. With the already large installed customer databases and their experiences in technologies (Miguel & Jorge, 2019).

The effect of the accelerated adoption of FinTech, due to disruptive events, on the role of traditional banks

To answer the last sub-question, a survey study and descriptive statistics are used to measure to what extent disruptive events have on the accelerated adoption of FinTech and by that a changing role of traditional banks. To measure this, advantage is taken from the current disruptive event Corona and its potential impact on FinTech adoption. In the survey, the participants are asked at first if they started to pay less in cash and more via online methods due to Corona. The outcome was that more than 70% of the participants have been using more FinTech since the beginning of Corona. This is in line with previous studies conducted this year about the increasing use of FinTech (contactless payments) during Corona (Wójcik & Ioannou, 2020); (Arner D. , et al., 2020). In addition, the participants indicate that on average they bought more products online since the start of Corona. It could be argued that these findings only apply during Corona, but the following finding contradict this. Namely, 91% of the participants indicate that they will probably still use the FinTech after the pandemic.

DISCUSSION

The entrance of Big Tech is good for the entire market because Big Tech companies will be a new competitor which benefits the consumers. Keep in mind the risk that Big Tech may monopolize the financial market within a few years. A traditional bank can't compete with the accumulated vast amounts of customer data about preferences and habits in combination with financial data. A monopolization will result in financial instability and a decrease in customer welfare (Miguel & Jorge, 2019). To prevent that this happens, traditional banks should change their approach when it comes to three sets of activities namely: transmuting the characteristics of financial assets and liabilities, providing payment services, collecting and processing information. Currently, FinTech companies can provide the same services as traditional banks but with less cost. This is mainly because of less regulations but also because of better technologies (Giorgio, Giacomo & Alberto, 2017).

The fact that FinTech delivers better technologies at a lower cost increases the adoption rate for Big Tech and puts pressure on the role of the traditional bank. However, when banks implement the new FinTech technologies themselves and combine this with their large customer databases, they will overcome FinTech companies and gain competitive advantages

Besides Big Tech, disruptive events as well accelerate the adoption of FinTech. After the financial crisis of 2008 people lost trust in banks. This resulted in a higher adoption rate for FinTech some even believe that without the financial crisis and the new regulations which came from it FinTech wouldn't even exist (Douglas & Armin, 2018). Another disruptive event that affected the adoption rate of FinTech is the COVID-19 pandemic. Since the outbreak in March 2020 FinTech has helped to keep the financial system going with innovative technologies and by facilitating financial flows in an online mode (Arner D., et al., 2020). Disruptive events like a financial crisis and a pandemic have a positive effect on the adoption of FinTech and they accelerate the process of the entry of Big Tech companies in the banking sector. We can say that disruptive events can be a starting point or acceleration for new technologies like FinTech.

Survey research found that over 70% of the respondents have started to pay less in cash since the COVID-19 outbreak in March 2020. More than 50% of respondents choose convenience over privacy and that they would rather use FinTech from Big Tech companies than FinTech from banks if the FinTech of Big Tech is easier to use. This as well shows that the adoption rate of FinTech during Covid-19 and since the entrance of Big Tech has accelerated. And that the role of the traditional bank might change and has to adopt FinTech themselves to keep customers.

Finally, we observed that the findings of the survey also agree with the findings in the literature analysis. There are however some limitations on our survey research.

Limitations

In this study there are (potential) limitations. These limitations are caused by the short time period in which this research is conducted and the limited availability of resources. Secondly there was a lack of access to data sources, in the limited time data was collected and this is sufficient to answer the research questions in this study but due to probability sampling and the relatively low sample this data could be unreliable. The survey is only conducted in the Netherlands, which could also influence the reliability and the generalizability.

CONCLUSION

Looking at the results and discussion the research question can be answered.

“What impact do disruptive events and the entry of Big Tech Companies in the banking sector have on the accelerated adoption of new financial technologies and the role of traditional banks?”

The banking sector will change in the upcoming years and FinTech will be one of the main factors behind the movement. The traditional bank will have a big competitor in Big Tech companies who are more experienced and are better set up to deliver convenient financial technologies to end-users. The entry of Big Tech companies will lead to an accelerated adoption of FinTech because of their brands, mix of technologies and existing customer base. Disruptive events like the Financial crisis in 2008 and COVID-19 accelerate the adoption of FinTech as well. The crisis in 2008 was the starting point for FinTech and the COVID-19 pandemic makes FinTech an essential part of the financial infrastructure.

The combination of a disruptive event and the entry of Big Tech companies seem to accelerate the adoption of FinTech even more as seen in the results. The role of the traditional bank will change over the upcoming years. Traditional banks will have to adopt FinTech themselves to stay relevant to their customers. Law and regulations might stop Big Tech companies from monopolizing the financial market but they will still be competitors of traditional banks in some capacity.

The insights gained by this research will be useful for bankers and other research in the growing impact of BigTech.

Further research

Future research should look into the mix of technologies Big Tech companies use to create an advantage in FinTech. The research should look into how effective this mix actually is and if the specific mix is anti-competitive and results in a monopoly. The future research should as well look into if taking out some technologies would make Big Tech FinTech more competitive and specify which technologies are most important.

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APPENDIX

Table 2. Survey Question

Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, I have started to pay less in cash and more via other payment methods like credit/debit card/Apple Pay.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020 I've bought more products online.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
The COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020 forced me to use new technologies like video calls (Microsoft teams, Zoom, etc.) and I will probably keep using them after the pandemic.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020 I've started to use new financial technologies like Apple Pay, Tikkie, etc.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
I trust a traditional bank more than I trust a Big Tech company (Google, Facebook, etc.).						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
When I'm leaving the house I always take my phone with me.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
I think convenience is more important than privacy when using technology.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
I only want a Financial institution like a bank to handle my financial information.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
I will probably use FinTech made by Big Tech companies (Google, Facebook, etc.) instead of Fintech made by my bank if the Big Tech FinTech is easier to use.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree
Big Tech companies should not be allowed to enter the banking sector if this ends up in a monopoly position.						
Strongly disagree	2	1	0	+1	+2	Strongly agree